

Major Trends in Kingdom Church Growth in Nigeria

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Abstract:

This paper discusses the major trends in the history of church growth and development in Nigeria. It adapts the recent work by Adamolekun (2012), showing five periods of the history of church growth in Nigeria. The paper discusses further the implications of church growth in Nigeria and offers some suggestions and recommendations that will help strengthen the church of God in Nigeria. The methodology adopted is a historical approach, relying mainly on secondary sources. This paper discovers that church planting has helped the growth of the church in Nigeria and that Pentecostal churches are at the forefront of church planting. It also discovers that the proliferation of churches has negative impacts. The paper concludes that there should be a controlled mechanism in place to curb the excesses of some church founders and that the growth of the church should not be based on orthodoxy but biblical orthopraxy so as to change the battered face of Nigerian Society for the better and help the image of the church of God not only in Nigeria but also in the entire world.

Keywords: christianity, history, church growth, Nigeria, christian missions.

Introduction

Historical discussion on church growth is important for four main reasons: one, to know where the church is coming from—how it started; two, to know where the church is now—the current state of the church; third, to know where the church is going—the future of the church; and four, to proffer panaceas to both implicit and explicit problems facing the church, and ultimately improve on the existing good results. Christianity is one of the major and strongest religions in Nigeria. I found the frank statements of Bob Passantino (1992) very useful and helpful, particularly when he declared that:

Christianity is unique among all of the religions of the world. All religions make sweeping claims about truth and reality and yet none except Christianity can point to historical evidence to verify those assertions¹.

The historicity of religion reveals that Christianity arrived on the soil of Nigeria in the 15th century. No doubt, since its arrival, “Christianity is making remarkable strides, not only in numerical growth but in the deepening theological maturity of many outstanding leaders”² in Nigeria. The presence of Christianity in Nigeria, especially since September 1842, has, in no small measure, culminated in the proliferation of churches in every part of the country.

Thus, the thrust of this paper is to discuss the history of church growth in Nigeria. Many scholars describe three phases or periods of church growth in Nigeria. But the recent work by Adamolekun³ shows five phases of the history of church growth in Nigeria. This is beautifully outlined as follows: the period of introducing Latin Christianity in the 15th and 16th centuries; the period of Denominationalism and missionary activities in the 19th century from 1842 onward; the period of evolution of Independent churches, the period of Indigenous African Churches; and the period of the birth of Charismatic and Pentecostal churches in Nigeria.

Therefore, this paper is set to discuss the history of church growth along this line for the purpose of clarity. The paper adapts Adamolekun’s five divisions of the history of church growth in Nigeria. This is because this author finds Adamelekun’s approach most interesting, unique, lucid, systematic, and comprehensive. The paper concludes with implications for the proliferation of churches in Nigeria, and suggestions and recommendations are also offered for further research.

¹ Bob Passantino. *Contend Earnestly For The Faith How Far Can We Trust The Bible?* , Copyright 1992. See also Ilesanmi, Dele, *Reliability of Canon*, unpublished work, 2020.

² Galadima and Turaki. *Christianity in Nigeria, Part 1* in *Africa Journal of Evangelical Theology*, 20.1, 2001.

³ This is beautifully illustrated in his work titled “*Main Trends in the Church Growth in Nigeria*” published in *European Scientific Journal* October edition vol. 8, No.23 ISSN: 1857 – 7881 (Print) e - ISSN 1857- 7431 3

Major Trends in Kingdom Church Growth in Nigeria

First Period (1st Phase): The Introduction of Latin Christianity

According to Fafunwa (1974), the first Europeans to set foot on the soil of what is now called Nigeria were the Portuguese⁴. "As early as 1472, Portuguese merchants visited Lagos and Benin and exchanged greetings with the Oba of Benin"⁵. Historical facts abound that Benin and Warri in the Niger Delta axis were the first areas to witness the first missionary presence in Nigeria⁶. History also shows that this initial European attempt to plant Christianity in Benin failed. There are many reasons for this failure. Citing Baur (2009), Rimamsikwe and Hilary (2013) stated that one of the reasons for the failure was that "The Kings of Benin City remained strongly attached to their indigenous religion"⁷ Adamelekun (2012) confirms this by stating that at that period, "Christianity failed to gain any permanent foothold in Benin, Warri, Bonny, and Calabar"⁸. There are other factors that culminated in the failure, as clearly stated by some eminent scholars like Ryder, Ade Ajayi, Erivwo, Lamin Sanneh, and Peter Clark⁹. The final settlement of the Portuguese in the Bight of Benin started in the 1480s¹⁰.

Christianity came to Benin Kingdom by accident, purposely for "some trade dealings"¹¹. Adamolekun (2012) corroborates this when he writes:

Christianity was introduced into the kingdom of Benin by accident. It was accidental because the Portuguese were in the West Coast of Africa primarily to trade in gold, ivory, pepper and slave. As a Christian nation, they aimed at the ultimate conversion to the catholic faith in their trading partners. Thus, the king and the authorities of the Roman Catholic Church at home encouraged them. Secondly the Portuguese sought the conversion of their native trading partners ...as Christians ...¹²

Missionary activities began in Benin City, Nigeria, in 1515, when some Catholic Missionaries set up a school in the Oba of Benin's Palace for his sons and the sons of his chiefs, who were already converted to Christianity¹³. Missionary activity in the 15th century was spasmodic, or rather minimal, because the preponderant commercial interest in the slave trade and pepper took prominence. Though the 16th century witnessed a remarkable interest in missionary activities on the part of the Portuguese, the Oba of Benin, named Esigie (1504-1550), sent an embassy to King Manuel of Portugal in 1514, and in the following year Christian Priests

⁴ Fafunwa, Babs. *History of Education in Nigeria*, (NPS Educational Limited, 1974): 71

⁵ Ibid.,

⁶ Rimamsikwe and Hilary, *Religion in Nigeria from 1900-2013*, in *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol.3, No.18, 2013

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Adamolekun, Taiye (2012), *Main Trends in the Church Growth in Nigeria*

⁹ Omotoye, Rotimi Williams. *A Critical Examination of the Activities of Pentecostal Churches in National Development in Nigeria*, 2010.

¹⁰ This is clearly explained in Adamolekun's *Main Trends in the church Growth in Nigeria, 2012*

¹¹ See Fafunwa. (1974): 71 for better understanding

¹² Op.cit.2012, here, Adamolekun cited Ryder to explain his points for a better grasp of the situation

¹³ Ilesanmi, Dele. *Ekiti and the Role of Roman Catholic Mission in Girl-Child Education since 1912*, in *Unswerving Mater Christi Girl: The Glory of Ekiti State* (Mater Christi Press Club, 2009): 26-27; see also Fafunwa.(1974) : 72

arrived in Benin. Citing Egharevba, Adamolekun “recorded that churches were built, the Oba’s son and some noblemen were baptized, and they started to learn how to read and write. Esigie’s successor, Orhoghua, was said to have been educated by the Portuguese in their school and was baptized”¹⁴.

Through the influence of the Portuguese traders, the Catholic missionaries were the first missionaries to come to Nigeria. They established a seminary on the Island of Sao Tome off the coast of Nigeria as early as 1571 to train Africans for God’s and the church’s work as priests and teachers to bring the people closer to God. From Sao Tome, the Catholic missionaries visited Warri, where they established schools and preached the gospel of Christ in the area. Though, according to Fafunwa (1974) and Ilesanmi (2009), this influence was nearly wiped out by the slave trade, which emaciated or devastated West Africa for almost 300 years¹⁵. Worse still, slaves were exchanged for guns-power, silk, alcohol, firearms, and so on. The chief foreign participants in this despicable or heinous act were the Portuguese, the English, the French, the Dutch, and the Danish¹⁶.

What is more, Adamolekun writes:

Mid-Sixteenth Century, the Itsekiris had become rivals to the Benin in slave trade, and when the Portuguese Missionaries were spurned in Benin in the period, they were welcomed by the Itsekiri rulers and the kingdom developed through contact with the Europeans under the direction of the Bishop of SaoTome, Gasper Cao (1556-1565, 1571-1574). Christianity was introduced to Warri by a company of Augustinian Monks sent to Warri, who founded a Christian settlement, named Santo Augustino. The first success of the Augustinian Missionaries was sent to Portugal in 1600 to be educated, and returned to Warri some years later with a noble Portuguese wife and three priests¹⁷.

All scholars agree that the first attempt to plant Christianity on the soil of Nigeria, in Benin, did not yet bear any lasting fruit. Even though, according to Galadima and Turaki, similar attempts were made at entering Borno and Hausa lands by Roman Catholics and Protestants alike, no fruitful result recorded¹⁸

Second Period (2nd Phase): The Period of Denominationalism and Missionary Activities.

According to Ilesanmi (2012), this second missionary activities to Nigeria was the most popular one, which was marked by the advent of the English speaking Christian mission in the land of Badagry, Lagos, Nigeria on 24th September, 1842. He stresses that the Roman Catholics were not left out in the “spiritual scramble” for Nigeria¹⁹. This missionary endeavor was a successful one which gave birth to the growth of the church in Nigeria.

¹⁴ Op.cit. Adamolekun. 2012.

¹⁵ Op.cit., see Fafunwa ,1974, and Ilesanmi (2009) for more understanding.

¹⁶ See Fafunwa, 1974, p.72 for details.

¹⁷ Op.cit., see Adamolekun, 2012.

¹⁸ Galadima and Turaki, 2001.

¹⁹ Op.cit., Ilesanmi, 2009, cited Fafunwa , 1974.

After the abolition of the slave trade, there was a fresh religious enthusiasm among the Europeans and Americans, and with the support of the missionary bodies, the freed slaves in places like Sierra Leone and Abeokuta encouraged missionary enterprises. This period was regarded as a period of denominationalism when many churches from the British Isles and America sent missionaries to the coast and interior of Nigeria²⁰. It should be noted that the Anglicans under the Church Missionary Society (CMS) were the first, but the Niger Expedition in which they came in 1841 failed²¹. However, the first successful penetration of Christian mission into the interior of Nigeria was made in 1842, when the Wesleyan Methodists, on the invitation of the freed slaves who had settled at Badagry and Abeokuta, sent Rev. Thomas Birch Freeman and an assistant, William de Craft, and his wife from the Gold Coast (Ghana), to Badagry, and some months later, Henry Townsend, to Abeokuta, for the purpose of Christianizing Nigeria²².

For the purpose of record, Ade Ajayi mentioned in his work, *Christian Missions in Nigeria*, as cited by Omotoye (2010), that

The C.M.S. was the largest and the most significant in this period. Being part of the established Church and based in London. It had the greatest influence in the British government. They established their mission in Badagry in 1845 and they led the expansion into the Yoruba country²³

Omotoye views the European Christian Missionaries second attempt in the 19th century as a way of Christianizing Nigeria²⁴. He reiterates that the Christianization of Nigeria between the 19th and 21st centuries came in two phases:

The first phase was led by the Methodist mission in September, 1842 under the leadership of Thomas Birch Freeman.⁸ He entered Abeokuta through Badagry which became an entreport to Yorubaland. The town of Abeokuta became the “sunrise within the tropics”. He was followed closely by Henry Townsend, a missionary of the Church Missionary Society (Anglican), who equally settled in Abeokuta in December, 1842.⁹ The missionaries were given a rousing welcome and hospitality by Sodeke, the traditional ruler of Abeokuta. These earlier missionaries were followed by the Baptist and Roman Catholic in the evangelization of Yorubaland. The Christian Missionaries equally visited the Eastern part of Nigeria almost at the time they visited Yorubaland. The Christian missionary enterprise was delayed in the Northern part of the country because of religious and political factors²⁵.

²⁰ Op.cit., Adamolekun

²¹ Ibid.,

²² Ibid.

²³ Op.cit., Omotoye, 2010.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

By extension, Adamolekun brings us to the history of church growth in the South South of Nigeria. He says that in the southern part of Nigeria, on the Cross River in the old slave-trading town of Calabar, the Presbyterians sent Rev. Hope Masterton Waddell, accompanied by Mr. and Mrs. Edgerl A. Chishalm and E. Miller, who arrived in Calabar in April 1846, to establish the church of Scotland Mission²⁶. The work of the Presbyterians was said to be very successful because the Presbytery of Biafra was created in 1858.

In 1850, the American Baptist Missionary, Rev. Thomas J. Bowen, arrived in Badagary to begin work in Nigeria. The attempt of Rev. Thomas J. Bowen, the Pioneer Missionary, to establish missions in Ketu and Iseyin was unsuccessful. He finally settled in Ijaye, where he built his first station²⁷. It was recorded that other Baptist missionaries who joined Bowen in Ijaye fell ill and died²⁸. Nonetheless, Rev. Thomas J. Bowen, in 1854, established a mission in Ogbomoso. That same year, an American negro from Liberia, J.M. Harden, joined the Baptist group and established a Baptist mission in Lagos. The Baptist mission later extended its influence to some parts of Yorubaland like Oyo, Shaki, Igboho, and Ilorin²⁹. The Roman Catholic Mission was not left out in the spiritual scramble for the souls of the people of Nigeria, through the Society of the African Missions, which came in 1862.

The ex-slaves were organized and stations established in Lagos and Abeokuta. When the Italian Priest, Father Broghero, visited Lagos in 1863, there was a catholic church in Yorubaland. The Holy Ghost Fathers started work among the Igbo of Eastern Nigeria in 1885 through Father Joseph Lutz working at Onitsha. Samuel A. Bill started the Qua Iboe Mission in the Qua Iboe River area from 1887, though it was not until 1891 that the Qua Iboe church was established as an Independent evangelical and inter-denominational body.

Mission work in Northern Nigerian started in 1893 through Rolland Bingham, Walter Gowans, and Thomas Kent in 1904, the Sudan United Mission (SUM) joined the Sudan Interior Mission (SIM) in the mission work in the North, concentrating in the regions of Adamawa, Benue and Bornu. It is to be noted that this period was characterized by missionaries' activities being based on denominations and limited to the Southern part of the country³⁰

During this second phase of church growth in Nigeria, the missionaries who came were well trained and really prepared for the work of the gospel of Christ in a tropical climate like Nigeria. They faced a lot of challenges, and many met their waterloo because of the rather unfavourable or malignant climate. The language barrier that had existed was reduced to the barest minimum by the use of interpreters and the missionaries themselves learning the language³¹. Besides, trained Nigerian Ministers started to emerge; more churches,

²⁶ Op.ci. Adamolekun, 2012

²⁷ Op.cit., Fafunwa, 1974, p.79

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Op.cit. Adamolekun, 2012

³¹ Ibid.

schools and hospitals were erected. In addition, and more importantly, more converts were baptised as an indelible mark in the new faith they had embraced and the old ways they had abandoned³².

For a quick review of the most important pioneering Christian missions in Nigeria with their dates, it will be sufficed to present them thus (see Galadima and Turak, 2001, citing Foxall, p. 257):

Wesleyan Methodist, 1842
Scottish Presbyterian, 1842
Church Missionary Society, 1844
Southern Baptist Foreign Mission, 1850
Roman Catholic Mission, 1961[sic] 1861/2
Sudan Interior Mission, 1893
Sudan United Mission, 1904
United Missionary Society, 1905
Seventh Day Adventist, 1914
Qua Iboe Mission, 1932[sic] 1887
Assembly of God, 1939
African Church Movements, 1888-1925

The establishment of churches by various missions has led to the growth of the church in Nigeria. This is evidenced in the work of Galadima and Turak, 2001:

By the 1970's, there were more than 50 Mission Agencies which operated in Nigeria. As a result of the work of many Christian missions, Christianity has grown and become one of the dominant religions in Nigeria. Over 45% of the population of Nigeria embraces Christianity. The Church Missionary Society (CMS), the Methodist and the Baptists pioneered mission work in the West, while the Presbyterian, the Catholics, and the Qua Iboe Mission pioneered the work in the East³³.

3rd Period (3rd Phase): The Period of Evolution of Independent Churches

During this third period of church growth, especially towards the end of the nineteenth century and the early part of the twentieth century, many churches in Nigeria witnessed schisms that culminated in the establishment of independent churches. These schisms occurred as a result of many factors, such as the transfer of workers, alleged oppression, and marginalization by white ministers among others. The white ministers were accused of viewing churches in Nigeria as part of the colonial legacies given to them by the British Crown³⁴. Adebisi (2003) says that the first schism started in the Eastern part of the Niger, followed by various other schisms in other parts of the country³⁵. He writes:

For instance, there had been a trouble ... in the Presbyterian Church in Calabar, which was led by Mojola Agbebi, who formed

³² Ibid.

³³ Op.cit., Galadima and Turaki, 2001

³⁴ Peter A. Adebisi, *History of Christianity in Ekitiland* (Published by CSS Press, 2003)p.125

³⁵ Ibid.

the Native Baptist Church and founded many churches in the Niger Delta area and in other places, including Igede-Ekiti and many parts of Ekitiland. Also in Lagos, the United Native African Church (U.N.A.) broke away in August 1891. ... Another crisis came from the Niger area where the late Bishop Ajayi Crowther had worked and built several churches and made thousand of converts.³⁶

It is to be noted that the broken away Native Baptists were brought back into association with the American Baptist Mission in 1894. In 1901, the African Bethel church was constituted in Ebute Metta, Lagos, by some members of St. Paul's Breadfruit church, Lagos, who had become displeased with the administration of the church by the white leaders. "A similar situation led to the formulation of the United African Methodist church (Eleja) in 1917, after seceding from the Methodist Church, Ereko, Lagos"³⁷.

The emergence of African Churches was as a result of agitation for African leadership and identity in the church and a protest against the condemnation of certain African Cultural practices by European Missionaries³⁸. This and many other reasons prompted Rev. Dr. Agbebi Mojola to fight back. Ilesanmi (2022) gives a comprehensive account of this in his book titled, *African Christianity and Nationalism: The Biography of Dr. Mojola Agbebi (1860-1917), The Moses of Africa*. It suffices to present an inkling of Dr Mojola Agbebi's repulsiveness here:

While Dr. Mojola Agbebi saw the introduction of Christianity by white westerners as an important step in the progress of African peoples, he argued that the introductory phase was over and that it was time for Africans to infuse Christianity with their spirit. Through African appreciation and performance of Christian songs, Agbebi called for a distinctive African religious voice: "We have come to the times when religious developments demand original songs and original tunes from the African Christian." Dr. Mojola Agbebi, was a prominent critic of white Christianity in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century³⁹.

Ilesanmi writes further:

Between 1880 and 1914, he sat on the editorial chairs of nearly all major Lagos newspapers. He was an astute editor, an excellent writer, and a fine preacher of note. No doubt, Dr. Mojola Agbebi created one of the most powerful "Africanization" movements of Christianity in colonial West Africa

The emergence of this Ekiti illustrious cerebral mini-Paul, "the Moses of African Christianity and pan-Africanism and

³⁶ This is comprehensively explained in this book published by Bishop Adebisi Peter, *History of Christianity in Ekitiland, 2003*.

³⁷ Op.cit., Adamolekun

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Ilesanmi, Dele Alaba (2022), *African Christianity and Nationalism: The Biography of Dr. Mojola Agbebi (1860-1917), The Moses of Africa*

nationalism”, Dr. Mojola Agbebi, like a meteor in the firmament of Christian missions in 1889 with his hard-hitting work titled “Africa and the Gospel”, his vitriol of tongue and pen became galling to the negrophobic American missionaries. His intellectual apogee was in his expository paper titled “The West Africa Problem “at the Universal Racial Congress held at the University of London. This, in no doubt, with other vituperations, coming from African intellectual caterpillar, Dr. Mojola Agbebi, with his sole aim to lead his people to Canaan land, away from the Babylonian captivity of European-American racial and cultural imperialism, mental enslavement, and spiritual subjugation, gave the American missionaries a coup de grace that eventually brought them to their knees⁴⁰.

Dr. Mojola Agbebi (formerly referred to as David Vincent) epitomizes his argument against white imperialism when he makes this classic statement: “To render Christianity indigenous to Africa, it must be watered by native hands, pruned by native hatchets, and tended with native earth”⁴¹.

Fourth Period (4th Phase): The Period of Indigenous African Churches

This fourth phase of Christian missionary activities vis-à-vis church growth, to be examined in this paper, is the *Aladura* Churches. These Churches include the Cherubim and Seraphim Church (C&S), the Church of the Lord (*Aladura*), the Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C.), and the Celestial Church of Christ (C.C.C.). They are all referred to as indigenous African Churches, and they were founded by Nigerians. Quoting Akin Omoyajowo, Omotoye (2010) writes: “the *Aladura* Churches are Churches which began the indigenous Churches, founded by indigenous persons, and run under indigenous leadership”⁴². These Churches were under the leadership of the following people: Moses Orimolade, Josiah Olunowo Oshitelu, Joseph Ayo Babalola, and Samuel Oshoffa, respectively⁴³. The word *Aladura* means, the person who is fond of prayer. In Yoruba, the word “prayer” means *adura*. If we now say *Aladura* church, we mean a praying church. These churches devoted much time to prayer.

The *Aladura* Churches combined the two fundamental elements of Christianity and African culture, in a way that advertised their Christian intentions without undermining their African credentials. They emphasized, or rather contextualized, some Christian practices that are relevant and valued by the African people, such as, prophecy, healing, prayer, vision, dreams, and the use of sacred objects. Within a few years of existence, most especially, between 1920’s-1960’s, the *Aladura* Churches grew phenomenally in every part of Yorubaland and beyond⁴⁴.

The *Aladura* Movement emerged in the 1920s. It is an African Nigerian initiative to carve out an identity for the African people, especially the Yoruba in the western part of Nigeria. This movement was essentially a 20th century phenomenon, and it represented, as observed by Omoyajowo cited by Adamolekun:

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Ibid.

⁴² Op.cit., Omotoye, 2010

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Ibid.

A reaction against the European complexion of the Western-oriented churches with their completely prefabricated theology and Christianity from their own perspective and to worship as Christian⁴⁵

Adamolekun continues:

This movement came with the “experience of direct communication with the Holy Spirit” The churches that started from this movement according to their own official etiology had different origins, but they had the common goal and desire to evangelize Africa by their own methods. The movement started immediately after the First World War. The influenza epidemic that broke out in the Southern part of Nigeria in 1918 rendered Western medicine impotent and the churches were closed by a government decree to curtail the spread of the epidemic⁴⁶.

There was an exponential growth in the number of churches planted in Nigeria between 1920 and 1960. No doubt, the *Aladura* movement contributed greatly to this growth. Indeed, there was no missionary factor in this movement. The indigenous churches in this category have many characteristics in common. Their founders had at one time or another been members of the Mission churches; they claim to have received direct inspiration from the Holy Spirit in establishing the churches; they all have strong convictions in the efficacy of prayers; hence, they were called *Aladura* (praying) churches. They prayed with a hand bell to communicate a start, break, or stop while praying because they prayed loud and fervently, which is antithetical to white’s idiosyncratic prayer life. They arose from the large towns of Yorubaland, and then spread to other parts of the country. Polygamy was not discouraged or encouraged in these churches, and Yoruba pagan practices were frowned at⁴⁷. Even though some did not see syncretism as a sin, they still held to the tenet of one living God. For example, there was a common saying at Osi-Ekiti, a Yoruba town in present-day Ekiti State, that *aimeji igbagbo li’ku pe lalede Osi*, meaning that “the one who does not know how to practice two religions (syncretism or bitheism) dies suddenly in Osi land. No doubt, these *Aladura* churches promoted Christianity, but with a local blend.

Fifth Period (5th Phase): The Period of Charismatic Evangelical and Pentecostal Churches

Pentecostalism emerged as a major brand and force of Christianity shortly after the independence of Nigeria in 1960, even though there was “*passive Pentecostalism*”⁴⁸ (Pentecostalism in the toga of “*Aladuralism*”⁴⁹) before this time. It is a major force that cannot be pushed aside globally. “The Pentecostal movement has emerged from small bands of revival seekers to become one of the largest Christian groups in the world”⁵⁰. Incidentally,

⁴⁵ Op.cit. Adamolekun, 2012

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ This term, “passive Pentecostalism”, is coined by this author, Dele Ilesanmi, to explain the spirit of Pentecostalism in *Aladura* churches. Pentecostalism is passive in *Aladura* churches.

⁴⁹ “Aladuralism” is a term coined by this author, Dele Ilesanmi, to explain that the *Aladura* churches believe in prayer and the Holy Spirit. Both Pentecostalism and *Aladuralism* emphasize the role of the Holy Spirit.

⁵⁰ See <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/26793612-pentecostalism-and-globalization> retrieved 14/03/2023

Nigeria proclaims the greatest Pentecostal credentials in African content⁵¹. Pentecostalism derived its name from the event of Pentecost in the Book of Acts of the Apostles 2:1-13, where the disciples were filled with the Holy Ghost on the day of Pentecost⁵². In fact, any church or Christian movement that stresses the experience of the Holy Spirit and the practice of spiritual gift is described or regarded as being Pentecostal⁵³. Gwamna (2017) describes the important role Pentecostalism plays in providing a cushion where government fails to meet the needs of the people:

Pentecostal rise and growth is understood as “redemptive”, “restorationist”, “interventionist” and salvific (eschatological) where the state seemed to have failed to provide the basic necessities of life, such as water, good roads, housing, security, education, food, and so on⁵⁴.

The revival of the 1930s had a positive effect on African Churches, especially in Yorubaland. We can invariably say that charismatic evangelical churches started during this period. Though this was the period of the *Aladura* Movement (the indigenous Churches), the spirit of Pentecostalism was in the air, in the toga of *Aladuralism*, which is a prerequisite to Pentecostalism. Pentecostalism is an offshoot of *Aladuralism*. Both Pentecostalism and *Aladuralism* emphasize the role of the Holy Spirit. We can say that Pentecostalism is a "rescued mission" for the mainline churches not only in Nigeria but also globally. This is succinctly explained by Steven M. Studebaker (2010) in his book titled *Pentecostalism and Globalization: The Impact of Globalization on Pentecostal Theology and Ministry*: "At a time when mainline denominations are engaged in massive closures of small rural churches, independent charismatics are strategically helping to rechurch rural Canada."

Indeed, Christianity has witnessed phenomenal growth in the establishment of Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria. Christian churches have become uncountable in number. This phenomenal growth is divine. What is more, the Pentecostal churches allow the Holy Spirit to have His way in their churches. This is the reason Pentecostal believers pray in an unknown tongue:

It is argued by Chris Obi, quoting Larry Christensen that Pentecostal Churches are seen as: “a supernatural manifestation of the Holy Spirit, whereby the believer speaks forth in a language he never learned, and which he does not understand”⁵⁵

⁵¹ Gwamna Dogara Je’adayibe, *Pentecostalism and Political Involvement in Nigeria*, in Spectrum, Journal of Contemporary Christianity and Society, Babatunde Adedibu (ed.) et al.,(Johnhny Jes Limited, Nigeria, Vol.2, No.2, October, 2017)p.126

⁵² Dairo, Afolorunso Olalekan, “...Being in the World and not Part of the World” *The Changing Face of Pentecostalism in the 21st Century Nigeria*” in Spectrum, Journal of Contemporary Christianity and Society, Babatunde Adedibu (ed.) et al.,(Johnhny Jes Limited, Nigeria, Vol.2, No.1, April, 2017)p.45

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ Op.cit., Gwamna Dogara Je’adayibe, 2017, p.129

⁵⁵ Op.cit., Omotoye, 2010

It is to be noted here that no church can claim “the exclusive repository of the Holy Spirit,” as posited by Omotoye in his work, because the promise in the book of Prophet Joel and Acts of the Apostles is meant for all Christian believers in Jesus Christ⁵⁶. Omotoye went further to quote Ruth Marshall thus:

One of the most remarkable trends of the last decade among the Christian population of Southern Nigeria has been the dramatic rise of the so-called “Charismatic” or “Pentecostal” movement.⁵⁷

Unarguably, Pentecostalism galvanizes church growth exponentially in Nigeria. It is also to be noted that some of these Pentecostal churches often started as "Christian fellowship" centers before they metamorphosed into full-fledged Churches, such as the Redeemed Christian Church of God (Pastor E. Adeboye, formerly Pa Rev. Josia Akindayomi, the founder), based in Lagos, which now has its headquarters in Redemption City of God, Lagos-Ibadan, Express way, Mowe, Ogun State; the Deeper Life Bible Church with the headquarters in Lagos, under the leadership of Pastor W. Kumuyi, Ogun State; Living Faith (Winners) being led by Bishop David Oyedepo (Otta, Ogun State); Rhema Church (George Adeboye, Ilorin); New Testament Church (Pastor M.R. Popoola, Ilorin); Trumpeters Church, Pastor T. Oludare, Ilesa; Church of God Mission, Benin-City, was founded by the late Benson Idahosa and is now being led by his wife, Bishop Margaret Idahosa. Others are the Household of God’s Church, Oregun, Lagos (Revd. Gabriel Oduyemi); Pastor Partrick Anwuzia’s Zoe Ministries; Pastor Tunde Bakare’s Latter Rain Assembly; Revd. Tunde Joda’s Christ Chapel International; Bishop Francis Wale Oke’s Sword of the Spirits; Prophet T.B. Joshua of Synagogues Church of All Nations; Pastor Chris Oyakhilome of Christ Embassy Church; the Dominion Life Bible Church (Pastor Bode Amoo) Ilorin⁵⁸, including Pastor (Dr) Paul Enenche of Dunamis, and many more Pentecostal churches are springing up daily. Pentecostalism is a threat to the kingdom of darkness in Nigeria.

Other reasons can be adduced for the vintage position of Pentecostalism vis-à-vis church growth in Nigeria. The influx of American Christian literature into Nigeria and American gossellers and freelance evangelists such as T.L. Osborn, Oral Roberts, Billy Graham, Kenneth Hagin, Gordon Lindsay, Morris Cerullo, and many others, coupled with the visits of Some of these above-mentioned evangelists to Nigeria, the crusades conducted by these great men of God, the sending of free tracts and booklets to the country⁵⁹; and many other foreign churches with Pentecostal outlook, promote Pentecostal movement in Nigeria:

For example in 1973, Reggy Thomas of the Revival Fires and T.L. Osborn conducted crusades at Ibadan, while Brothers Argemiro of the Free Gospel Mission conducted revival in Lagos. “The year came to an end with a powerful crusade conducted by Morris Cerullo on December 15th 1973 at Ibadan⁶⁰

Adamolekun posits:

⁵⁶ See Omotoye, 2010

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ Op.cit., Adamolekun

⁶⁰ Ibid.

A prominent feature of these crusades which gave rise to the emergence of separatist evangelical Christian groups, were instances of the divine healing, the baptism of the Holy Spirit and other Pentecostal manifestations, which appealed mostly to the youths that formed the majority of the population of the crowd gathering at these crusades. The revivals and crusades were the avenues by which Pentecostalism was introduced into the country.

Adamolekun continues:

The resultant effect of the crusades and revivals was the spirit of protests from the youths in the established churches in which they complained that their parents' churches were not spiritual enough, new churches thus spring up here and there with different purposes. Among the churches that were established on the basis of the explanation made above, include: The Redeem Christian Church, Deeper Life Bible church, Evangelical Church, of Yahmey, Church of God, Mission Agape Church, End Time Evangelical Ministry, Christian Charismatic Ministries (CCM); Born Again Gospel Church, and many others, Some churches were established for genuine reason of evangelism (e.g. Deeper Life, Redeem Christian Church, Christian Charismatic Ministry (CCM) and Gospel Faith Mission) while some were established for commercial purposes. This scenario led to the birth of proliferation of churches.

Implications of the Proliferation of Churches for Church Growth in Nigeria

This section centres on the positive and negative impacts or implications of the proliferation of churches in Nigeria. It is no more news that Christianity or the Christian church has contributed immensely to the progress of Nigeria than any other religious sect, spiritually, educationally, economically, socially, and politically. Omotoye observed that Christianity is a catalyst for social change in any society. Citing J.D.Y. Peel, he said, "New needs, values, techniques, and roles, new political, economic, and religious systems are interconnected yet not wholly dependent on one another"⁶¹. To encapsulate the positive impact of the proliferation of churches in Nigeria, we can come to the conclusion that this has helped in providing:

1. Spiritual and moral development
2. Employment generation
3. Educational development
4. Humanitarian services
5. Social and ethical development
6. Improved economy
7. Political development
8. Poverty alleviation
9. Reduction of corruption

As good as the proliferation of churches may be, there are also negative impacts of this trend. As scholars of Christian religion and theology, we are duty-bound to critically consider the activities of these churches because the gospel of Jesus Christ that we know is gradually being given a new interpretation and/or coloration every day. We can summarize succinctly the negative implications of the proliferation of churches in Nigeria as follows: The doctrinal differences that emanate as a result of split usually confuse many members of the Christian body; some churches are established for commercial purposes with the aim of enriching the founders and not for salvific reason; some church founders use diabolical means to draw people to their churches and enrich themselves; some ministers of God are not well trained; some so called ministers of God claimed to be called but for the purpose of their stomachs; teaching of heresies because there is no control mechanism for this proliferation; prosperity preachers are more than holiness or salvation preachers; many independent churches have become cesspits of corruption and fundraising; many of these churches are money conscious and politically driven ministries; and so on.

In spite of the negative impacts listed above, the proliferation of churches has done more good than harm. In fact, the proliferation of churches has led to the birth and growth of churches in Nigeria. It is to be noted that the Redeemed Christian Church of God, as one of the fastest-growing churches in the world, has the largest employees in Nigeria, next to the government, with well-paid pastors. To corroborate this, the General Overseer of the mission, Pastor E.A. Adeboye, said in one of the services held at the Redemption Camp (now Redemption City of God) a few years ago that "our pastors are well-paid; if you see any church that pays more than what we pay our pastors, we will double what we pay our pastors." This clearly shows that the church has contributed to the economic lives of people. Thus, the proliferation of churches should be encouraged.

⁶¹ Opt.cit., Omotoye, 2010

Suggestions and Recommendations

For further research on the history of church growth in Nigeria, the following suggestions and recommendations are offered:

1. More research should be conducted to prove the need for the establishment of more churches.
2. Establishment of more schools by churches to provide manpower for national development;
3. More churches should be planted to bring those who are in darkness to light.
4. Churches should focus more on the salvation of souls than prosperity messages.
5. There should be a controlled mechanism in place to checkmate the excesses of some church founders.
6. Pastors should be well-trained before manning a church, especially in the areas of ministerial ethics, theology, and apologetics.
7. Christian Social Responsibility should be intensified in all churches.
8. Christians should be more involved in politics to bring Christ to Nigerian politics and politics;
9. Christians should be their brothers' keepers and be good examples to non-Christians.
10. Churches should agree on biblical doctrines, not human doctrine.
11. The growth of the church should not be based on orthodoxy but biblical orthopraxy, so as to change the battered face of Nigerian Society for the better.

Conclusion

This paper has been able to discuss the history of church growth in five phases, adapting Taiye Adamolekun's five periods of church growth. The five are: the period of introducing Latin Christianity in the 15th and 16th centuries; the period of Denominationalism and missionary activities in the 19th century from 1842 onward; the period of the evolution of Independent churches; the period of Indigenous African Churches; and the period of the birth of charismatic and Pentecostal churches in Nigeria. In addition, the paper outlined the implications of the proliferation of churches in Nigeria and concluded with some suggestions and recommendations that will help move the church of God forward in Nigeria. Unarguably, Churches in Nigeria have humble beginnings with good intentions. No doubt, the church brought light to Nigeria in particular, Africa, and the entire world in general. Both traditional and Islamic religions had been in practice on the soil of Nigeria for years before the advent of Christianity. Yet Christianity brought light to Nigeria and the entire continent. The planting of churches or Christianity on African soil has helped (and is still helping) benighted Africans from their primitive dungeon of life to a redemptive age of survival through the help of foreign Christian missionaries and the power of a benign God. Today, these foreign Christian nations and powers are now reaping what they sowed in Africa; Africans are now replanting Christianity in their lands. For example, the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) has over 500 parishes in the UK alone, the US, and many other European and Asian countries. The RCCG has planted parishes in not less than 197 nations of the world, with over 50,000 parishes and over 9 million members⁶². This is even enough to prove that the proliferation of churches is a plus for church growth.

⁶²Check www.rccg.org for more achievements of the church.

For the purpose of emphasis, there should be a controlled mechanism in place to curb the excesses of some church founders, and the growth of the church should not be based on orthodoxy but biblical orthopraxy so as to change the battered face of Nigerian Society for the better and help the image of the church of God not only in Nigeria but also in the entire world. Furthermore, the discussion on the history of church growth here is not exhaustive. It is hoped, therefore, that more research work will be conducted to discover more facts and expand the academic horizons on this subject.

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